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Co-ordination, balance, proprioception and core stability exercises among football players in terms of prevention of injuries and improvement of performance: A randomised trial

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Abstract

Questions: What was the effect of Co-ordination, Balance, Proprioception and Core stability exercises training in terms of prevention of injuries and performance of the football players?

Design: Randomised Trial.

Participants: Thirty football players aged 15 to 17 years with no recent injury.

Interventions: Two teams had been measured with height, weight and BMI. In addition, players in the experimental group were preferred a regimen of Co-ordination, Balance, Proprioception and Core stability training to be performed four times per week for 4 weeks.

Outcome measures: The primary outcome was the prevention of injuries during the match. The secondary outcome was the performance of players.

Results: The average Ladder drill (Cardiovascular endurance) achieved for 3.58 seconds with a standard deviation of 0.95, the average 40 yard speed test achieved 4.77 with standard deviation of 0.05, the average Agility T-Test achieved 16.76 with standard deviation of 0.58 and the average Wingate Power Test achieved 11.52 Watts/Kg with standard deviation of 0.89 in Experimental Group. The average Ladder drill (Cardiovascular endurance) achieved for 4, 14 seconds with a standard deviation of 0.59, the average 40 yard speed test achieved 4.83 with standard deviation of 0.07, the average Agility T-Test achieved 17.41 with standard deviation of 0.44 and the average Wingate Power Test achieved 10.80 Watts/Kg with standard deviation of 0.75 in Control Group. This mean difference is in cardiovascular endurance statistically significant, $p = 0.062$. This mean difference is in 40 Yard Speed Test statistically significant, $p = 0.012$. This mean difference is in Agility T-Test statistically significant, $p = 0.012$. This mean difference is in Wingate Power Test statistically significant, $p = 0.023$.

Conclusion: This study showed that Co-ordination, Balance, Proprioception and Core stability exercises are effective and feasible method of reducing number of injuries in football players. These exercises may help the young football players from unnecessary injuries during the match.

Trial Registration: BKLWRMC/IEC/483/2022.

Keywords: Co-ordination, balance, proprioception, core stability training, football players

Introduction

Football is an open-skill, competitive sport that calls for a variety of perceptual, cognitive, and motor skills to be used in constantly shifting environments. A task or activity that requires voluntary control, has a specific purpose or goal to achieve, and must be completed with high confidence and the least amount of time and/or energy can be described as requiring a skill^[1]. Younger, preadolescent players are more likely to sustain injuries in youth soccer, also known as football outside of the United States, than in many other contact or collision sports. Young males tend to sustain more ankle injuries than young females do when it comes to musculoskeletal injuries. Soccer players frequently sustain concussions from contact or collisions rather than through deliberate action at heading the ball^[2].

The most popular sport in the world is soccer. Expectedly, soccer-related injuries occur frequently and place a heavy burden on individuals, families, the socioeconomic and healthcare systems, as well as on their physical and financial well-being. We provide a succinct summary of the most recent scientific data on injury rates, characteristics, mechanisms, risk and protective factors, prevention interventions, and implementation of interventions in soccer using well-established injury prevention frameworks^[3]. 9.31 injuries were reported for every 1000 athlete exposures overall.

The majority of injuries (17.5%), blocking (15.8%), and tacking occurred during general play (14.0). The three most frequently reported injuries were hamstring tears (4.7%), lateral ligament complex tears (6.9%), and concussions (7.5%).

The ability to coordinate one's feet and eyes is crucial in football. The Institute of Neurology in London has confirmed that vision is what moves the foot. Players with good foot-eye coordination are able to dribble the ball, make accurate free kicks, fool the defence, and make pinpoint passes. A player's ability to stop a soccer ball with his foot and make adjustments to intercept it is another benefit of foot-eye coordination [51].

Balance can be static or dynamic and is generally defined as the capacity to keep the centre of gravity of the body within the base of support. The capacity to maintain the body in a state of static equilibrium or within its base of support is known as static balance. Because it requires the capacity to maintain equilibrium during a change from a dynamic to a static state, dynamic balance is thought to be more difficult to achieve. Effective integration of visual, vestibular, and proprioceptive inputs is necessary for both static and dynamic balance in order to generate an efferent response that controls the body within its base of support [61].

Proprioceptors, which are found in muscles, ligaments, and joints to sense muscular tension and stretching, are a component of the proprioceptive system. The brain processes the data and sends it to the muscles so they can adjust as necessary. The risk of injury to the knees and ankles, among other places, is probably reduced. Proprioceptive programmes can help reduce risk not only for newly injured soccer players, but also for players who have a high propensity for injury [71].

The most popular training technique used by football players to improve their strength performance is core training. In training programmes, core training has been a popular and successful strategy in recent years. Because they are situated in the centre of the body, the core muscles are actively involved in the majority of movements. A new training approach, particularly in terms of performance improvement, is defined as core training, which supports the spine and actively contributes to the integrity of muscle groups that are effective in developing upper extremity strength. Another name for core training is a method of exercise that enables the strengthening of the muscles in the lumbopelvic hip region, which are important for core stability. To increase a person's flexibility, anatomical function, balance, and strength, core training is typically preferred. Additionally, while core training promotes structural improvements in the muscles, it also aids neural adaptation. Additionally, by enhancing the proprioceptive senses and promoting muscle development and body control, core training increases fundamental stability and strength [81].

Hence, the purpose of the study to find out the effect of Co-ordination, Balance, Proprioception and Core stability exercises in order to prevent injuries and performance of football players.

Method

Study Design

Randomized Trial, enrolled players were who underwent Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire (PAR-Q). On day one, players were randomly allocated to one of two groups via a computer-generated, concealed allocation schedule.

Participants

This research was conducted at the SVJCT's Sports Academy. Players referred to the SVJCT's Sports Academy Football Ground in November 2022. The study protocol was approved by institutional scientific and ethics committee of SVJCT's BKL Walawalkar college of Physiotherapy, Sawarde, Maharashtra before the commencement of study. The total sample size for this study was 30 Football Players with normal physique.

Intervention

Team consists of 15 players attended an individual session with a Physiotherapist to learn how to effectively do the usual Football training program with and without Co-ordination, Balance, Proprioception and Core stability exercises during warm up period in terms of prevention of Injuries. The training protocol for both interventions comprised the same standardised educational and exercise components.

The inclusion criteria were age between 15 to 17 years Football Players with normal Physique in male only, no recent injury or lower extremity pain from almost six months and they had no history of vertebral column surgery in their lifetime.

The exclusion criteria were Football Players having, Scoliosis, Kyphosis, Lordosis, Chronic low back pain, musculoskeletal injuries from last six months, any mental disorders, and limb length discrepancy.

The study was conducted in SVJCT's BKL Sports Complex Grass Football Ground in Walawalkar Campus. Two teams had been selected from SVJCT's CBSE School who are studying 9th and 10th standard. All 30 players had undergone football training under same coach. The coach had trained the two teams in football field. The two teams had been divided into two groups i.e experimental group (n-15) and control group (n-15) by random allocation method. The informed consent was taken from all players prior to the assessment. Pre-participation screening was done using Physical Readiness Questionnaire (PAR-Q form) Performa for assessment was filled by the interviewing the players which include information about Age, Gender, Height, Weight, BMI, Dominant leg for kick, Years of experience, history of injury and surgery. Team one (Experimental Group) will be trained usual Football training program with the coordination, proprioception, balance and core training exercises and Team two (Control Group) will be trained in usual Football training program only.

Experimental group

The Team one (experimental group) intervention consisted of co-ordination, balance, proprioception and core stability training exercises in addition to a usual football training program provided by a student physiotherapist. The Each Co-ordination exercise, Balance exercise, Proprioception exercise, and Core training consist of Rapid Response Stationary Speed Cones and Hurdles Drills (6 sets for 15 seconds), side lunge (10 rep in each leg), Wobble board squats (10 rep × 1,2 & 3 sets) and Knee Tuck Crunches (10 rep × 1,2 & 3 sets) respectively. The total training session would last for 30 to 45 minutes 4 times per week for a month. In Rapid Response Stationary Speed Cones and Hurdles Drills, The 10 cones had been placed in line 1 feet distance between each cone similarly, the 10 hurdles had been placed in line 1 feet distance between each hurdle. The team were

asked to side run on cones line for 3 times and further jump over the hurdle and run for 3 times totally 6 sets within 15 seconds. Then, team were instructed to do side lunch for 10 repetitions in each leg. Later, team were allowed to do squats on wobble board for 10 repetitions in 3 sets. Finally, team were encouraged to do knee tuck crunches for 10 repetitions in 3 sets. These all exercises had been worked out in one session. Like this, 4 sessions per week for 4 weeks. Along with these exercises, the players had been practised with usual football training program.

The team were assessed with hamstring/quadriceps ratio by manual muscle testing (MMT), Cardiovascular endurance by Ladder drills in secs, Speed by 40 Yard test in secs, Agility by T-Test in secs and Power by Wingate Test in watts/kg. All the values were noted before the play.

Control group

Players in the control group were not shown, taught or prescribed the co-ordination, balance, proprioception and core stability training exercises that were prescribed for the experimental group. The players in Control group were undergone usual football training program only such as stretches, cardio, strengthening exercises etc. Initially, the players were allowed to do general body stretches from top to bottom of all muscles. Then, the players were asked to run for 15 minutes to add up the cardio respiratory endurance in their physique. Later, players were instructed to strengthen their lower limbs by doing home bound strengthening exercises such as Heel raise, Marching, Mini Squat, Step up etc. In heel raise, the players were asked to lift their heels and hold it for 10 seconds in 10 repetitions. In Marching, the players were asked to raise their knees up to waist level repeatedly and alternatively for 1 minute. In Mini squat, the players were instructed to squat half and hold it for 10 seconds in 10 repetitions. Finally, in Step up, the players were asked to step on the staircase repeatedly and alternatively for 1 minute. These all exercises had been worked out in one session. Like this, 4 sessions per week for 4 weeks.

After four weeks training program, Pre-Match screening was done using questionnaire and scale which includes Position of Player, Hamstring/Quadriceps Ratio, Cardiovascular endurance (lateral in out by secs), Speed (by 40 yard Test by secs), Agility (T-Test by secs) and Power (Wingate Test by Watt.Kg⁻¹). Later, the football match was held between Experimental group (n-15) and Control group (n-15) for 1 hour that consists of 30 minutes each session. 10 minutes break between two sessions. The Full Match was recorded by Camera for analysing performance of Team. During the play, the number of injuries such as Quadriceps Strain, Hamstring Strain, Calf Strain, Ankle Sprain and ACL Tear had been noted down. Post-Match screening was done using Performance questionnaire such as Ball Possession, Passing Accuracy, Number of Tackles, Number of Saves and Number of Shots.

Outcome measures

Primary outcome

The primary outcome was to assess the number of injuries in various parts of player's body during the football match by numerical scale.

Secondary outcome

The secondary outcome was to assess the various skills of players by observation.

Data analysis

Collected data were entered in excel software and analysed used R software version 4.0.1. Continuous variables were presented as mean and standard deviation and categorical variables were presented as count and per cent. Paired t-test was done to compare the means between the experimental group and the control group. $p < 0.05$ were considered statistically significant.

Results

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of the Players

Characteristics	Experimental Group (n=15)		Control group (n=15)	
	Average	SD	Average	SD
Age (Years)	15.80	0.41	16.07	0.26
BMI (Kg/m ²)	19.38	2.63	20.37	3.99

Fig 1: Cardiovascular endurance (Ladder Drills) (secs)

Fig 2: Speed (40 Yard Test) (secs)

Fig 3: Agility (T-Test) (secs)

Fig 3: Power (Wingate Test) (watts/kg)

Table 1 provides baseline Characteristics of the Players in both experimental and control group. In experimental group, the average age group was 15.8 years, the average height was 161.53 cm, the average weight was 50.53 kg and the average BMI was 19.38 kg/m². In control group, the average age group was 16.07 years, the average height was 158.73 cm, the average weight was 52.2 kg and the average BMI was 20.37 kg/m².

Figures provides values of outcome variables done in both experimental and control group. The average age is 15.80 with standard deviation of 0.41, the average BMI is 19.38 with standard deviation of 2.63, the average Ladder drill (Cardiovascular endurance) achieved for 3.58 seconds with a standard deviation of 0.95, the average 40 yard speed test achieved 4.77 with standard deviation of 0.05, the average Agility T-Test achieved 16.76 with standard deviation of 0.58 and the average Wingate Power Test achieved 11.52 Watts/Kg with standard deviation of 0.89 in Experimental Group. The average age is 16.07 with standard deviation of 0.26, the average BMI is 20.37 with standard deviation of 3.99, the average Ladder drill (Cardiovascular endurance) achieved for 4, 14 seconds with a standard deviation of 0.59, the average 40 yard speed test achieved 4.83 with standard deviation of 0.07, the average Agility T-Test achieved 17.41 with standard deviation of 0.44 and the average Wingate Power Test achieved 10.80 Watts/Kg with standard deviation of 0.75 in Control Group. This mean difference is in cardiovascular endurance statistically significant, $p = 0.062$. This mean difference is in 40 Yard Speed Test statistically significant, $p = 0.012$. This mean difference is in Agility T-Test statistically significant, $p = 0.012$. This mean difference is in Wingate Power Test statistically significant, $p = 0.023$.

Discussion

This randomised trial is the first to analyze the effects of Co-ordination, Balance, Proprioception and Core stability training among the football players in order to prevent the injuries and improve the performance of the players. The analyses of the trial's data estimate that the average effect of the exercise program in this population is to reduce the number of injuries. Furthermore, the exercise program leads to improve the player's performance. Therefore, the exercise program could play a major role in prevention of injuries during the football match. Finally, outcome values were compared with baseline values. It showed that significant changes were between these values.

It has been demonstrated that using coordination drills along with structured football training is an efficient way to enhance general football ability in players between the ages of 10 and

13 males ^[9]. For the effectiveness of exercise-based programmes to prevent soccer injuries, conflicting evidence has been found. Different study populations (in terms of sex and soccer type) in the included studies, differences in the intervention programmes that were implemented (in terms of content, training frequency and duration), and programme compliance are a few possible explanations for the contradictory results. To effectively lower the incidence of injuries in soccer, high-quality studies examining the best kind and intensity of exercises in a general training programme are required ^[10]. A dynamic warm-up programme that incorporates preventive exercises before games or training sessions, as well as the addition of strength, balance, and mobility training to the training sessions, are two ways that football players can reduce the incidence of match and training injuries ^[11]. In football, there was evidence that the FIFA injury prevention programmes were more effective at preventing injuries than controls. This effect was included by the FIFA 11+ prevention programme, which reduced football injuries by 39% and has a significant injury-preventing effect, whereas the FIFA 11 prevention program's preventive effect could not be proven ^[12]. This study showed that after a 6-week exercise programme, young football players with poor knee control showed no statistically significant differences in dynamic knee valgus angles and dynamic balance values ^[13]. This meta-analysis shows that balance training, either by itself or in conjunction with other injury prevention methods, reduces the risk of ankle injuries ^[14]. IAI-Programme can offer more sensitive advantages than FIFA11+ in terms of the proprioceptive ability of knee flexion and CMJ. Improvements in the dynamic postural control as determined by the LSDT can be seen in the IAI-Programme and FIFA11+ ^[15]. Resistance training is argued to be ineffective because it improves muscle stretch reflexes, which may lessen co-contraction, and yields no decreases in the times required for voluntary activation and the time to peak torque. However, it is believed that stability and balance training reduces muscle stretch reflexes, which in turn improves co-contraction. Additionally, stability and balance exercises that activate the ligaments and capsular receptors in the knee joint may strengthen co-contraction patterns to promote even greater gains in joint stabilisation. The reductions in voluntary activation times and times to peak torque that result from stability, balance, and plyometric training may shorten players' muscle response times, enabling them to execute quick and unexpected sports manoeuvres. Training regimens that focus on these neuromuscular mechanisms may improve anterior cruciate ligament protection ^[16]. The findings show that pre-participation warm-up exercise increased knee-joint-position sense acuity while fatigue from a football game decreased it ^[17]. A multicomponent injury prevention training programme may be appropriate for reducing the number of muscle injuries during a season, but it may not be sufficient to reduce all other injuries, according to the study's findings ^[18]. For improving lower extremity flexibility during a single training session, structured neuromuscular training with a longer duration is superior to training with a shorter duration ^[19]. Effective preventive training programmes significantly lower severe knee injuries in elite football. Programs specifically tailored to the needs of the playing level and the preferences of the coaches are essential for the sustainability of preventive training measures ^[20].

This study offers useful support for combining core exercises for the best balance and strength development of the lower limbs in young soccer players ^[21]. According to recent

research, injuries may be more likely to occur when core stability is compromised and injuries may be less likely with the right training. Utilizing isometric, isokinetic, and isoinertial techniques, core stability can be evaluated. Back and lower extremity injury rates may go down as a result of appropriate intervention, according to [22]. Soccer players who sustain a lower extremity sprain or strain without contact have lower core endurance than healthy players. Injury incidence is correlated with decreased core endurance. Enhancing side-bridge hold time in particular could lower injury risks [23]. After building a statistical model, this study identified measures for dynamic postural control, core muscle strength, and core muscle endurance as important risk factors for the emergence of overuse injuries. Proprioception, functional movement, and core neuromuscular control, however, might not enable clinicians to recognise patients at risk. These easily available, trustworthy screening tools could be applied in clinical settings for overuse injury screening and injury prevention. Given the low relative predictive accuracy (53%), it is important to exercise caution when predicting injuries using this model [24].

Limitations

This research study has a few limitations done on smaller group of healthy volunteer football players. Moreover, this Co-ordination, Balance, Proprioception and Core stability exercises used single time for this study.

Conclusion

This study showed that Co-ordination, Balance, Proprioception and Core stability exercises are effective and feasible method of reducing number of injuries in football players. These exercises may help the young football players from unnecessary injuries during the match. Further studies are required to confirm this result with professional football player population and could explore over the Hockey Players, Basketball Players, and Rugby Players.

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Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest among the authors.

References

1. Souglis AG, Travlos AK, Andronikos G. The effect of proprioceptive training on technical soccer skills in female soccer. *International Journal of Sports Science & Coaching*; c2022.
2. Koutures CG, Gregory AJ. American Academy of Pediatrics. Council on Sports Medicine and Fitness. Injuries in youth soccer. *Pediatrics*. 2010;125(2):410-4.
3. Owoye OBA, Vander Wey MJ, Pike I. Reducing Injuries in Soccer (Football): an Umbrella Review of Best Evidence Across the Epidemiological Framework for Prevention. *Sports Med Open*. 2020;6(1):46.
4. Chandran A, Morris SN, Powell JR, Boltz AJ, Robison HJ, Collins CL. Epidemiology of Injuries in National Collegiate Athletic Association Men's Football: 2014-2015 Through 2018-2019. *J Athl Train*. 2021;56(7):643-650.
5. Wilson Tiu, Charrie Lee Salipot, Charissa Anna Maquiraya, Doris Maria Burkley, Michiko Castaneda, Marie Grace Gomez. Effects of a modified football program in improving foot-eye coordination among students with intellectual disability. *Educational Research (ISSN: 2141-5161)* 2012;3(4):412-423.
6. Asimenia Gioftsidou, Paraskevi Malliou, Georgios Pafis, Anastasia Beneka, Kyriakos Tsapralis, Polina Sofokleous, *et al*. Balance training programs for soccer injuries prevention, *Journal of Human Sport and Exercise*. 2012;7(3):639-647.
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/263937386>
7. Francisco Tomás González-Fernández, Andrés Mármol Pérez, Francisco Tomás González Fernández, Andrés Mármol Pérez. Effect of proprioceptive training in male soccer players, *Journal of Novel Physiotherapy and Physical Rehabilitation*; c2020 Jul.
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343604240>
8. Ahmet Ath. The effect of a core training program applied on football players on some performance parameters, *Journal of Educational Issues ISSN 2377-2263*. 2021;7(1):337-350.
9. Köksal M, Gül GK, Doğanay M, Álvarez-García C. Effects of coordination training on the technical development in 10-/13-year-old football players. *J Sports Med Phys Fitness*. 2021;61(4):497-504.
10. Van Beijsterveldt AM, van der Horst N, van de Port IG, Backx FJ. How effective are exercise-based injury prevention programmes for soccer players? A systematic review. *Sports Med*. 2013;43(4):257-265.
11. Pérez-Gómez J, Adsuar JC, Alcaraz PE, Carlos-Vivas J. Physical exercises for preventing injuries among adult male football players: A systematic review. *J Sport Health Sci*. 2022;11(1):115-122.
12. Thorborg K, Krommes KK, Esteve E, Clausen MB, Bartels EM, Rathleff MS. Effect of specific exercise-based football injury prevention programmes on the overall injury rate in football: a systematic review and meta-analysis of the FIFA 11 and 11+ programmes. *Br J Sports Med*. 2017;51(7):562-571.
13. Wilczyński B, Wąż P, Zorena K. Impact of Three Strengthening Exercises on Dynamic Knee Valgus and Balance with Poor Knee Control among Young Football Players: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *Healthcare (Basel)*. 2021;9(5):558.
14. Al Attar WSA, Khaledi EH, Bakhsh JM, Faude O, Ghulam H, Sanders RH. Injury prevention programs that include balance training exercises reduce ankle injury rates among soccer players: a systematic review. *J Physiother*. 2022;68(3):165-173.
15. Navarro-Santana MJ, Asín-Izquierdo I, Gómez-Chiguano GF, Albert-Lucena D, Plaza-Manzano G, Pérez-Silvestre Á. Effects of two exercise programmes on joint position sense, dynamic balance and countermovement jump in male amateur football players. A randomised controlled trial. *J Sports Sci*. 2020;38(22):2620-2630.
16. Lloyd DG. Rationale for training programs to reduce anterior cruciate ligament injuries in Australian football. *J Orthop Sports Phys Ther*. 2001;31(11):645-54. discussion 661.
17. Salgado E, Ribeiro F, Oliveira J. Joint-position sense is altered by football pre-participation warm-up exercise and match induced fatigue. *Knee*. 2015;22(3):243-8.
18. Owen AL, Wong del P, Dellal A, Paul DJ, Orhant E, Collie S. Effect of an injury prevention program on muscle injuries in elite professional soccer. *J Strength Cond Res*. 2013;27(12):3275-85.
19. Rahlf AL, John C, Hamacher D, Zech A. Effects of a 10

- vs. 20-Min Injury Prevention Program on Neuromuscular and Functional Performance in Adolescent Football Players. *Front Physiol.* 2020;11:578866.
20. Krutsch W, Lehmann J, Jansen P, Angele P, Fellner B, Achenbach L, *et al.* Prevention of severe knee injuries in men's elite football by implementing specific training modules. *Knee Surg Sports Traumatol Arthrosc.* 2020;28(2):519-527.
 21. Dello Iacono A, Padulo J, Ayalon M. Core stability training on lower limb balance strength. *J Sports Sci.* 2016;34(7):671-8.
 22. Willson JD, Dougherty CP, Ireland ML, Davis IM. Core stability and its relationship to lower extremity function and injury. *J Am Acad Orthop Surg.* 2005;13(5):316-325.
 23. Abdallah AA, Mohamed NA, Hegazy MA. A Comparative Study of Core Musculature Endurance and Strength between Soccer Players with and Without Lower Extremity Sprain And Strain Injury. *Int J Sports Phys Ther.* 2019;14(4):525-536.
 24. De Blaiser C, De Ridder R, Willems T, Vanden Bossche L, Danneels L, Roosen P. Impaired Core Stability as a Risk Factor for the Development of Lower Extremity Overuse Injuries: A Prospective Cohort Study. *Am J Sports Med.* 2019;47(7):1713-1721.